

IMPORTANCE OF PASSIVE SOLAR DESIGN FOR CYPRUS

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ABSTRACT

Cyprus has no energy resources of its own. Therefore, more than 94% of the total primary energy is imported to the island creating not only ecological imbalance but also serious financial government credit. Passive solar design is a viable energy-saving concept that can be applied in the context of Cyprus. Renewable energy sources (biomass, hydroelectric, geothermal, wind, photovoltaic, active and passive solar) have been researched for the context of Cyprus, taking into consideration their advantages, disadvantages, financial feasibility, cost effectiveness and benefits. Due to the Cyprus's climate, financial budget and geographical potential the ideal energy source is passive solar. In an attempt to evaluate some of the current housing habits in Cyprus, two questionnaires were compiled. The outcome of both questionnaires suggests the need for better, more bioclimatically appropriate constructions. Priorities for research and action by which to co-ordinate passive solar applications with innovation planning are suggested. Of particular importance is the role of the Cyprus governmental or public policy in encouraging efforts in the private sector at the community and individual project level.

1. INTRODUCTION

Cyprus's climate is within the temperate Mediterranean zone. Its average hottest peak reaches 41°C in the summer and drops to an approximate of 5°C in the winter. Relative humidity ranges from 40-60%, and a large daily temperature range is noted with up to 18°C difference between day and night. Thus Cyprus's climate calls for the need of cooling in the summer, and for heating in winter.

With the exception of solar energy, Cyprus has no other energy resources of its own and has to rely heavily on fossil fuel imports. The energy consumption is predominantly oil based. The contribution of solar energy to meet the primary energy needs of the country is estimated to be 5.9%.¹ Thus, more than 94% of the total primary energy is supplied by

imports. The cost of imported energy represents 63% of the domestic exports. Due to the developmental nature of the economy of Cyprus energy consumption is increasing at an average annual rate, for the last ten years, at about 6.9%.

Figure Breakdown of the final electricity consumption to sectors of economic activity per year

The total annual energy consumption (electricity included by the domestic sector) in Cyprus comprises of 15.1% with electricity at 34%. Based on consumption by households, a rate of growth of 4.6% is indicated yearly. Breakdown of residential energy consumption in terms of final energy used (fig. 2) shows its large share of electricity consumption. In terms of end-use of energy in households (Table 3.4), water heating holds the highest place being half of the total consumption, and more than half of the electricity.

Table 3.4 End Uses of Energy in Households

Water heating	Heating	Lighting	Cooking	Electrical appliances
50%	18%	24%	3%	3%

The present construction trends indicating distinct preference to private, detached houses over apartment flats (60% prefer private detached houses), coupled with higher standard of living (70% of houses are built with central heating) imply a larger energy saving potential in this particular type of dwelling.

2. RENEWABLE ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES

The need for renewable energy sources is one of our country's greatest concerns. Renewable energy technologies harness energy sources such as sunlight, wind, water, and plant material. Unlike fossil fuels, these sources are self-replenishing and most often inexhaustible. Renewable energy technologies include:

2.1 Hydroelectricity

Hydropower is not used in Cyprus, mainly because of low rainfall in Cyprus. Though it is a non-polluting energy source, hydroelectric systems usually require a dam and a reservoir.

2.2 Biomass

Cyprus has investigated the possibility of building a power plant generating electricity with biomass. For a power plant with the capacity of 1.5MW continuously over one year, it is estimated that a total of 324 hectare of land will be needed. The company suggests that a Giant Reed is used. The grass has a robust root system that offers protection against soil erosion and provides oxygen to the soil. It is

also said to be extremely pest resistant thus not requiring any pesticides before or after harvesting. For irrigation (twice a month from June to September) treated sewage water is suggested².

2.3 Geothermal

In Cyprus, geothermal power plants do not exist, mainly because the geographical potential does not exist.

2.4 Wind Energy

Wind is an abundant source of clean mechanical and electrical energy. Some of the environmental concerns of using wind energy on a large scale are the land requirements, noise, and visual pollution. Careful wind machine design and siting, however, can reduce these impacts. Wind farms can be used for other purposes, such as agriculture and ranching. Two initial wind studies have been conducted for Cyprus^{3 4}, both indicating that mean wind speeds are enough for introducing wind energy.

2.5 Solar Thermal

Solar thermal systems typically concentrate sunlight to generate heat. This heat may be used directly for water and space heating, industrial processes, or to produce steam for operating electricity-production turbines. The most significant environmental impacts associated with solar thermal technologies are the great land area requirements and visual impacts of utility-scale systems. Cyprus has excellent conditions for grid connected solar thermal power generation. Appropriate site locations for solar thermal electricity are normally in arid to semi-arid countries situated in the sun-belt, which includes the Mediterranean region, and naturally Cyprus. A 100MW plant could generate close to 10% of today's consumed electricity in Cyprus.⁵

Solar ponds, a type of solar thermal technology, use layers of salt water of varying concentrations to trap heat. This heat can be used for a variety of purposes, including electricity generation, yet not in Cyprus. The most significant area of environmental concern with this technology is that if improperly sealed, ponds may pollute nearby land and water with salt.

2.6 Photovoltaics

The European Union⁶ estimates that an average of 16.3% of Europe's electricity needs in 1990 could be provided by stand-alone rooftop PV systems. In Cyprus, most homes are already grid connected. This means that the electricity is supplied via national grid. By utilizing the national grid, expense of the batteries can be avoided. The whole national

grid can be used as a giant battery. The Experimental solar house⁷ is the first grid connected house, with others following.

2.7 Active Solar Systems

Active solar heating systems commonly consist of solar collector panels, plus a storage medium to hold the heat collected during the day, and a set of automatic controls that monitor and regulate both heat collection and delivery between the storage medium and the living space. Most types of active systems require an auxiliary heating system to provide extra heat during extended periods of cloudiness or extreme cloudiness or extreme cold.

High-temperature solar collector panels may be used to power an Absorption-Chiller Air Conditioning. Such systems are relatively expensive but may be cost-effective in climates like Cyprus where plentiful sunshine and a substantial need for air conditioning exist. Also, Heat Pumps may be used in conjunction with solar panels. Solar heat boosts the heat pump's source during the winter, and during the summer the heat pump can discharge heat to the outdoors at night through the collectors.

At present, there are six major and twenty minor manufacturers of solar water heaters in Cyprus, employing a total of about 400 workers and producing about 11,000 units per year, compared to 4000 units prior to 1974⁸. The savings from the SWH represent about 4% of the annual primary energy consumption in 1988⁹. There is an established know-how of solar energy, as well as public acceptance of the technology.

The Cyprus government in recent years has helped the promotion of active solar energy by the following actions:

- o Making solar water heating mandatory in refugee housing.
- o Providing loans to individual and hoteliers for installation of solar water heaters.
- o Technical support: consisting of testing of collectors, advice to industry for improvement of products and to consumers for efficient utilisation.
- o Making the materials used for the construction of solar water heaters duty free.

All these measures have helped the promotion of solar water heaters. The technical support has been of increasing importance, becoming practically critical now that further expansion of market depends on quality and product diversification. It is about time to act the same way for passive solar energy. Air collectors with multiple uses (e.g. drying of agricultural products, heating of water, heating of

green houses, house heating) represent another large share of the future market.

2.8 Passive Solar Systems

A few Cypriot architects are now designing new houses and retrofitting older houses to passively use the sun and other environmental factors to reduce energy costs. In a temperate climate, a thermally passive building should include passive heating and cooling design options in such a combination that an optimum environment is established throughout the year. From a thermal environment standpoint, each inhabited building complex in Cyprus falls under one of the following categories:

- o The climate is totally ignored. The claim is that a climate sensitive design is not required because the climate extremes are not severe.
- o Only winter conditions are considered. The idea is to minimise the heating requirements in order to save in fuel and ignore the problem of overheating in summer.
- o The climatic constraints influence the design of the houses.

The experimental solar house¹⁰ has proven that a passive solar construction can indeed maintain steady indoor temperatures, regardless of outdoor conditions. It was also proved empirically that for the solar systems to be successful, the residents must be actively involved in operating the passive solar features.

- o The research has demonstrated that it is possible to design low-energy buildings and achieve high thermal comfort at the same time, as well as good indoor air quality, and low environmental impact. The research has shown that it is possible to reduce the total energy consumption to a small fraction of the typical consumption today. The average total projected energy consumption of the experimental building developed in the research is 44 kWh/m² per year. This is only about 25% of the typical consumption in residential buildings in Cyprus.
- o It is necessary to consider the total energy use, and not focus on space and/or water heating alone. It is, for example, important to consider both heating and cooling, as focusing on one season could only lead to problems during the other season. In addition, reducing cooling loads was often a greater challenge than reducing heating loads.
- o Passive solar systems can offer several benefits and give solar houses a market advantage. Sunspaces and daylighting systems add amenity value to the buildings and contribute to their energy performance when properly designed. Sunspaces are especially attractive in dwellings, where they can reduce space heating when used to preheat ventilation air.

- o Designing new, innovative building concepts requires a multi-disciplinary design team. The extensive uses of solar technologies, which are often integral parts of the design, make the design process different from traditional methods. It requires the energy aspects to be considered from the early design stage, and also requires the architects, engineers and the clients' collaboration from the beginning.
- o Training of constructors and on-site supervision is particularly important in low-energy buildings. In very low-energy buildings, the energy consumption is strongly influenced by construction practices and by user behaviour than in conventional buildings. For instance, air tightness and the avoidance of thermal bridges is much more important in a well-insulated building than in a traditional building.

3. BENEFITS OF PASSIVE SOLAR FOR CYPRUS

Within Cyprus in the coastal and central areas, energy needs for cooling can amount to two or three times those for heating, on an annual basis. Utilisation of the basic principles of heat transfer, coupled with the local climate, and exploitation of the physical properties of the construction materials, could make the control of the comfort conditions in the interior of buildings possible. Even in areas with average maximum ambient temperature around 31.7°C, comfortable conditions inside buildings can be achieved by means of proper building design¹¹ that frequently makes the use of air-conditioning units in dwellings unjustified.

Passive cooling strategies in the design of buildings in Cyprus should be considered, since the extensive use of air-conditioning units is associated with the following problems:

- Wide use of air-conditioning units has caused a shift in electrical energy consumption to the summer season and an increased peak electricity demand¹². Peak electric loads impose an additional strain on national grids, which can only be covered by development of extra new power plants.
- Increased electrical energy production contributes to exploitation of the finite fossil fuels, to atmospheric pollution and to climatological changes^{13 14}.
- Heat rejection during the production process (for electrical energy and air-conditioning units) and from the operation of air-conditioning units themselves, increases the phenomenon of the 'urban heat island'¹⁵
- Ozone-layer depletion can be caused by CFCs and HFCs (the most common refrigerants of currently used air-conditioning units) from possible leakage during manufacture, system maintenance or unit failure¹⁶.
- Increase indices of illness symptoms (lethargy, headache, blocked or runny nose, dry or sore eyes, dry throat and sometimes dry skin and asthma), known as 'sick building syndrome'¹⁷ is reported in people working in air-conditioned buildings.^{18 19}
- Occupants' dissatisfaction with indoors comfort conditions.
- Economic and political dependence of Cyprus with limited natural resources on other countries, richer in natural resources.
- Installation of air-conditioning units presents an extra cost in the construction of a building, followed by an additional operation and maintenance cost²⁰.
- Expenses for importation of A/C units: countries with hot climates exhibit an increased rate of sales of air-conditioning units. In Cyprus, sales of packaged air conditioning have increased by 900% over recent years²¹ with 80% of them delivered to the residential sector.²²

4. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS BASED ON QUESTIONNAIRES

In an attempt to evaluate some of the current housing habits in Cyprus, two questionnaires were compiled, one by the author and one by a young environmental group from the Secondary School of Linopetra. The results of both questionnaires were taken from contemporary residences with an average size of 200-250m², with mostly four or five residents, in urban areas of Lefkosia. Upon examining the outcome of the detailed questionnaire of the author, certain interesting observations are deduced:

- A high percentage (69%) of the survey participants experience bothersome noises from the outside, probably as a result of poorly insulated wall surfaces and single glazing which not only allow heat enter and exit freely, but also allow noise to penetrate with little difficulty.
- A high percentage of the participants frequently felt cold in the winter (80%) and an even greater number feel warm in the summer (87%).
- There were complains about bothersome cold surfaces (70%).
- Another problem area, which can be minimized by proper passive design, is the need for artificial lighting (64%).
- Participants experience drafts from windows and doors (86%)– an element of ventilation that can be exploited in a passive system, if it is designed properly.
- There is a need for a more widespread use of double-glazing windows in order to minimize moisture

condensation on windows (65%), and for a better thermal and noise control.

- An interesting fact deduced from the survey is that the overwhelming majority of Cypriots feel safe in and around their house (91%), which makes it easier for a passive solar designer to arrange for ventilation systems requiring frequent openings especially for nighttime ventilation.
- Another advantage the passive solar designer will have in Cyprus is the fact that the Cypriots seem to appreciate the use of shutters (87%), which have been used in traditional architecture.
- Of the 13% of participants who did not find shutters an acceptable means of controlling indoor temperatures, most attributed it to the fact the shutters do not work properly. This implies the need for shutters to be placed in front of windows more appropriately planned.
- The majority of dwellings have no insulation (66%).
- Of the houses that do have some insulation (34%), it mostly is in the form of double-glazed windows and reflective silver coatings (a waterproofing material, which is misunderstood to act as a thermal insulator) rather than in structural constructions, which implies that most insulation in the surveyed houses was more or less treated as an afterthought.

From the outcome of both questionnaires, it transpired that most dwellings in Cyprus are constructed with little or no insulation and this is the most likely cause for the high percentage of summer and winter discomfort as well as noise complaints. Most other complaints stated (e.g. poor natural lighting) are the result of unsuccessful bioclimatically orientated design. All this suggests the need for better, more bioclimatically appropriate constructions, with adequate insulation and proper orientation with respect to the sun.

5. HOW PASSIVE SOLAR DESIGN CAN BE WIDELY ADOPTED TO CYPRUS

The following steps could be used to guide any technical innovation program. These are particularly important to the further development and wider application of passive solar concepts to vastly different circumstances throughout Cyprus. Of particular importance is the role of the Cyprus governmental or public policy in encouraging efforts in the private sector at the community and individual project level. While the following steps are not proposed as a fixed decision sequence nor are all steps needed in all cases, they suggest priorities:

- o Establish a Cyprus Energy Resource Inventory. This is simply an analysis of the existing energy and resource

flows from without and within Cyprus, alongside an inventory of indigenous sources that could be developed for local needs. In addition to material resources, for which the inventory method is well known, local resources from the standpoint of energy conservation include available sun, wind, air and earth temperature and humidity, which are potential energy sources for heating, cooling and lighting buildings.

- o Undertake a Survey of Appropriate Energy Conserving Technologies for Cyprus. Many international methods of appropriate energy technology are known and these might be surveyed, once local resources are known and local needs identified. This suggests that there should be a worldwide and local “library” of current research and applications of passive solar innovation.
- o Establish Institutional Support for Integrated Innovation Initiatives. The type of institutional support required in each situation will depend on the specific case. Comprehensive innovation planning inevitably suggests that a number of improvements be initiated simultaneously, combining initiatives in urban services, in commercial enterprises, and in community development. These programs in turn might combine financial incentives, personnel training, outreach programs, and administrative innovations.
- o Initiate Prototype or Experimental Applications such as the experimental solar house. With any program that involves changes in both technical and social patterns, small-scale tests are needed so that the design can be corrected before proceeding too far. Different technological solutions might be tested simultaneously for each problem. An investment strategy might be to fund prototype and experimental costs only, since widespread dissemination would occur only if results could be further implemented without artificial subsidy.
- o Establish a Training and Dissemination Plan. Many energy-efficient designs for buildings do not result in energy savings because of the way they are used and maintained. As a result, education and training are necessary components of any energy-related technology transfer program and may require the extended efforts usually associated with long-term community development.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper set out to demonstrate that passive solar architecture is a viable energy-saving concept which can be applied in the context of Cyprus.

The application of the science and art of passive solar architecture to reduce the demand for thermal energy in a building represents a growing area. Retrofitting existing buildings and novel designs of new buildings to this end are

a major technical challenge to the near future for Cyprus. In the more distant future, solar ponds and photovoltaic power stations, wind turbines and biomass may make a significant contribution to the energy scene.

Throughout this research it has been concluded that, although all renewable energy sources have been considered (biomass, hydroelectric, geothermal, wind, solar, thermal, solar electric and active), the ideal energy-saving architectural technique for Cyprus is passive solar architecture. Cyprus's climate, financial budget and geographical potential does permit or causes various problems, with regards to all other renewable energy source, other than passive solar.

At this time, it can be argued that passive design is experiencing a maturity of design applications in which solar energy is utilised in heating, cooling and daylighting buildings. The message here to advance this important beginning, it is that passive design is a sophisticated process to reach simple solutions. Therefore the innovations to look for in the years ahead will be first the development of design methods to enable building professionals to identify balanced and practical solar designs, and second the development of variations of passive solar techniques suited to local climate and resource conditions. This could result to a clearer vision by everyone involved of how passive design is the most cost-effective strategy available in creating an environmentally sound habitat in the climate of Cyprus or any climate of the world. Because of Lefkosia's climate, passive solar architecture works to its full capacity. This means that, a passive solar house has 100% energy saving potential.

8. REFERENCES

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